

MIRZO SIROJ HAKIM VA UNING MEROSI.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684770>

Annotatsiya. XX asr boshlarida O'rta Osiyo yerlarida, jumladan, Buxoro amirligida jadidchilik harakati keng quloch yozdi. Ijtimoiy-siyosiy harakat o'z oldiga qo'ygan asosiy maqsadi Buxoro amirligi hududida ta'limni isloh qilish, yangi matbuot va adabiyotlarni tarqatish, asosiysi xalqni uyg'otishdan iborat edi. Jadidchilik harakatining ko'zga ko'ringan namoyandalardan biri, "Yosh Buxoroliklar" harakati a'zosi, bilimdon kishilaridan biri atoqli savdogar, sayyoh va doktor Mirzo Siroj Hakim edi. Ushbu maqolada Mirzo Siroj Hakim va uning merosi qisqacha tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: jadidchilik, "Yosh Buxoroliklar", sayohat, matbuot, gazeta, tibbiyot.

MIRZA SIROJ HAKIM AND HIS LEGACY.

Abstract. At the beginning of the 20th century, the Jadidist movement spread widely in the lands of Central Asia, including the Bukhara Emirate. The main goal of the socio-political movement is to reform education in the territory of the Bukhara Emirate, spread new press and literature, and the main thing is to awaken the people. was Mirzo Siroj Hakim, a famous merchant, tourist and doctor, was one of the prominent representatives of the Jadidchilik movement, a member of the "Yosh Bukharolikler" movement, and one of its knowledgeable people. This article briefly analyzes Mirza Siroj Hakim and his legacy.

Key words: struggle, "Yosh Bukharolikler", travel, press, newspaper, medicine.

МИРЗА СИРОДЖ ХАКИМ И ЕГО НАСЛЕДИЕ.

Аннотация. В начале XX века джадидистское движение широко распространилось в Средней Азии, включая Бухарский эмират. Основной целью общественно-политического движения было реформирование образования на территории Бухарского эмирата, распространение новой прессы и литературы, а главное было разбудить народ. состояло в расстреле. Мирзо Сиродж Hakim, известный купец, турист и врач, был одним из видных представителей движения Джадидчилик, членом движения «Йош Бухароликлер» и одним из его знающих людей. В этой статье кратко анализируется Мирза Сиродж Hakim и его наследие.

Ключевые слова: борьба, «Йош Бухароликлер», путешествие, пресса, газета, медицина.

Buxoro qadimdan ilm-u urfon markazi bo'lib kelgan. Mirzo Siroj 1877-yil 23-oktabrda Buxoroning Ismoilxo'ja mahallasida sarrof va savdogar oilasida tug'ilgan. Uning otasi hoji Abdurrauf Mirzoxurd juda boy va Buxoroda taniqli shaxs edi. U yolg'iz o'g'lining ta'lim olishini, faoliyatini davom ettirishini orzu qilardi. Shu bois u besh yoshidanoq o'g'lini ilm-fanga, san'atga yo'naltirishga alohida e'tibor bergan. Yosh Sirojiddin maktab va madrasa ilmlarini o'rgangach, ustozlari qo'lida axloq, tarix, adabiyot, arifmetika, geografiya, matematika, fors, turk, arab, rus, fransuz tillarini puxta o'rgandi. Shu bilan birga, u she'riyatga mehr qo'ydi, uning forsi she'rlari

Buxoro adabiy doirasi tomonidan yaxshi kutib olindi. U voyaga yetkach dastlabki faoliyatini otasining kichik bir sarroflik do'konida boshlab keyinchalik o'zi mustaqil ravishda paxta savdosi bilan shug'ullangan.

U ish yuzasidan Marg'ilon, Andijon, Jizzax, Toshkent, Chimkent, Jambul kabi shaharlarga ko'p sayohat qiladi, mahalliy turmush tarzi bilan tanishadi. Mirzo Siroj Sadridin Ayniy va Munzim tavsiyasi bilan Sadri Ziyon xonadonida o'z davrining mashhur kitobi – Ahmad Donishning “Navodir-ul-vakoe”si bilan tanishadi. Qori Rahmatullohi Vozehning “Savoneh-ul-masolik va farosix-ul-mamolik” (“Yo'llarning qulayliklari va mamlakatlarning masofalari”) (1887) asarini o'qish va turli xil savdogar va sayohatchilardan Rossiya imperiyasi, Usmonlilar davlati, Eron, Hindiston, Afg'oniston va ayniqsa Yevropa mamlakatlari ko'p ma'lumotlarni eshitishi yosh Sirojdin qalbida sayohat orzusini uyg'otadi. Mirzo Siroj 1902-1909-yillarda Yevropaning ko'plab mamlakatlarida, xususan, Avstriya, Vengriya, Bolgariya, Serbiya, Fransiya, Buyuk Britaniya, Italiya, Germaniya, Rossiya, Polsha va Eron kabi Sharq mamlakatlarida savdo qilgan.

Afg'oniston, Turkiya, Arabiston, Hindiston va boshqalarga sayohat qilgan. Mirzo Siroj 1902-yil 5-iyunda Buxoroda uchrashgan Avstriya shahzodasining taklifini bajarish bahonasida Yevropaga olti oylik safarga o'tlanadi. Turkman cho'li orqali Krasnovodskka, u yerdan Kaspiy dengizi bo'ylab Bokuga, u yerdan Tiflis va Batumiga boradi. Qora dengiz orqali Turkiyaga kelib, Samsun va Istanbul shaharlarini aylanib chiqadi. U yerdan Sofiya, Budapesht, Vena, Berlin, Parij, London, Bern, Marseille, Milan, Varshava, Moskvaga boradi va Ryazandan temir yo'l orqali Buxoroga qaytadi.

Mirzo Sirojning ikkinchi safari 1903 yilning mart oyida bo'lgan. Bu safar u Eronning bir qator shaharlari, jumladan Mashhad, Nishopur, Sabzavorga sayohat qilib, 1905-yil 16-iyunda vataniga qaytib keladi. Bu safar davomida u Sabzavor shahrida sakkiz oy qoladi. Keyin Hirot, Kobul va Mozori Sharifdan o'tadi. Sabzavor shahri haqida shunday deydi: “Sabzavor Xurosonning qudratli va obod shaharlaridan biridir. Shahar havosi juda yoqimli. Xurosonning boshqa shaharlariga nisbatan toza va ozoda. Sabzavorda bug'doy, arpa, paxta ko'p. Paxta va jun savdosi ham yuqori. Ko'plab mahalliy va xorijiy korxonalar mavjud. Sabzavordagi savdogarlarning aksariyati g'arbliklar. Tabrizda ham yirik bizneslari bor. Ular g'alla, yog' va shakar, choy va boshqalarni sotadilar, paxta va jun sotib oladilar. Sabzavor paxtasi Xurosonning boshqa shaharlaridan afzaldir”. Eronning boshqa bir shahri Mashhadga Mirzo Siroj biznes bilan shug'ullanishini aytadi: “Mashhadga ko'proq sayr qildim, oxiri zerikib ham ketdim va bir ish bilan shug'ullanishim kerakligini angladim. O'zimdagi pul, Qo'qondagi tijorat mollari va Xitoy bankinging biletlari va boshqalarini keltirib, bu yerda arzon bo'lgan paxta va terilarni sotib oldim.

Olgan narsalarimni Sabzavor, Nishopur va boshqa hududdan kelgan tijoratchilarga berdim, shu bahona Nishopurga ham borib sayr qildim”.

Mirzo Siroj 1905-yil iyulidan 1909-yil oxirigacha davom etgan uchinchi safari chog'ida Eron, Afg'oniston va Hindistonning qator shaharlarida bo'ladi. Eronda 1905-1911 yillardagi inqilobning bevosita guvohi bo'lgan. 1903 yilda Erondagi mashhur Tehron tibbiyot kolleji (hozirda Tehron tibbiyot universiteti)ga o'qishga kiradi. Uni tamomlab, kollejdagi o'qituvchilik va Mozandaron kasalxonalarining birida vrachlik faoliyatini olib boradi. Tez orada, Eronda “Doktor Mirxon” nomi bilan mashhur bo'ladi. Ko'p vaqt o'tmay, uning dovrug'ini eshitgan Afg'oniston

amiri Habibullaxon Mirzo Sirojiddinni ishga taklif etadi, u yerda "Doktor Sobir" nomi bilan faoliyat yuritib shuhrat qozonadi.

Mirzo Siroj 1909-yil dekabr oyida vataniga qaytgach, Buxoroda yevropacha kasalxonada ochadi va odamlarni yangicha davolashga kirishadi. Turli mamlakatlarga sayohat qilish, rivojlangan davlatlarning taraqqiyotini ko'rish, matbuoti bilan tanishish, boshqa xalqlar maorifchilarining asarlarini o'qigan Mirzo Sirojiddinning qalbida o'z yurtini tanazzuldan qutqarish va xalqni ma'rifatli qilish orzusini uyg'otadi. Shuning uchun u "Yosh Buxoroliklar" harakatining faol ishtirokchisi bo'ladi.

Mirzo Sirojiddin uzoq yillik safarlari davomida ko'rganlari va xotiralarini "Tuhafi ahli Buxoro" ("Buxoro ahlining tuhfalari") nomli asarida sodda va ravon tilda hikoya qilib qoldirgan. 1910-yilda muallif asarni qo'lyozma nusxasini yozib tugatgan va 1912 yilda esa Kogon bosmaxonasida toshbosma nusxasi nashr etilgan. Asarning qo'lyozma nusxasi fors tilida yevropa qog'ozida yozilgan. Jami bo'lib, 193 sahifani o'z ichiga oladi, uning o'lchami 13x20, yaxshi holatda, kirish va xotimasi bilan to'liq saqlangan.

Mirzo Siroj nafaqat ajoyib shoir va yozuvchi, balki mohir publitsist va jurnalist ham edi.[1]

U birinchi tojik tilidagi gazeta «Buxoro sharif»ning asoschilaridan biri bo'lib, uning sahifalarida ijtimoiy xarakterdagi she'r va maqolalari bilan chiqqan. Bu gazeta 1912-yilda Buxorolik yana bir ma'rifatparvar Mirzo Muhyiddin bilan birgalikda Kogon (Yangi Buxoro)da chop etilgan. Mirjalol Yusufzoda muharrirligi ostida 1912-yilning 14-iyuliga qadar haftada bir marta, keyinchalik esa haftada to'rt marta nashr etiladi. 1912-yilning iyulidan "Buxoroi Sharif"ga ilova tarzida eski o'zbek (turkiy) tilida "Turon" gazetasi nashr qilina boshlandi. "Turon" dastlab ilova tarzida haftada ikki marta chop etilgan, o'sha yilning sentyabridan esa mustaqil nashr sifatida faoliyat yurita boshlagan. Har ikki gazeta 2600 ("Buxoroi Sharif" — 800, "Turon" — 1800) nusxada nashr etilgan. "Buxoroi sharif" gazetasi oradan bir yil o'tib, 153-sonidan so'ng yopib qo'yiladi. Mirzo Sirojiddin "Buxoroi Sharif"ning ilk sonlaridan boshlab "Hakim Buxoriy" taxallusi bilan maqolalar e'lon qilib boradi. Masalan, "Ro'znomaning ba'zi foydalari" maqolasida gazetalar xalq dunyoqarashini o'zgartirishi, kitob mutolaasi, qanday yashashni o'rganish, dunyo yangiliklari va xalqlari ahvolidan xabardor bo'lish uchun eng muhim vosita ekanini ochib beradi.

Mirzo Sirojiddinning masnaviy usulida yozgan "Yod bod" ("Yodda bo'lsin") nomli she'ri 1913-yilda "Oyna" jurnalining 2-sonida chop etiladi. She'r va maqolalari Eronning "Navbahor" va "Tus", Turkistonning "Samarqand" gazetasi va "Oyna" jurnalida ham chop etilgan

Muallif o'z chiqishlarida tarixiy tafakkurni shakllantirish masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi. Allomalar yurti bo'lgan Markaziy Osiyoda ilm nufuzi pasayib ketgani, aholini savodli qilishdagi kamchiliklar va ta'lim tizimidagi muammolarni jiddiy tanqid qiladi. Buyuk ajdodlarimizga munosib avlod bo'lish uchun tarixdan to'g'ri saboq chiqarishimiz, ilm-fanni rivojlantirish, kitob o'qish lozimligini bayon etgan. Shuningdek, "Hifz-us-sihhat" sarlavhasi ostida tibbiyot va salomatlikka oid 30 dan ortiq qimmatli maqolalar e'lon qilgan.

Mirzo Siroj "Buxoroi Sharif" nashri orqali bir qancha jadid arboblari, jumladan Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy, Abdurrauf Fitrat, Abdulqodir Muhyiddinov bilan yaqindan tanishdi.

Mirzo Siroj 1913-yilda to'rtinchi marta sayohat qiladi, lekin yo'lda uning kasalligi kuchayib, 1913-yil 21-dekabrda Eronning Rasht shahridan Buxoroga qaytib keladi va bir yosh o'g'il bir qizcha otasi unda 1914-yil yanvar oyi o'rtalarida sil kasalligi tufayli vafot etadi. "Oyina"

jurnali bosh muharriri Mahmudxo‘ja Behbudiy Mirzo Siroj vafotidan so‘ng o‘zining majallasida “Ziyo‘i alim” (“Achchiq yo‘qotish”) degan maqolani chop etib ta‘ziya bildiradi. Shuningdek, Mirzo Siroj vafoti munosabati bilan “Oyna” jurnalining 14-sonida Sadridin Ayniyning qayg‘uli marsiyasi chop etiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, XX asr boshlarida Buxoro amirligida yashab ijod qilgan Mirzo Sirojiddinning ma‘rifatparvarlik qarashlari va uning “Tuhafi ahli Buxoro” asari komil inson tarbiyasida muhim o‘rin egallaydi.

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